

SERVICE OF REPRESENTATIVES OF MODERN SINGING ARTS IN KARAKALPAK MUSICAL CULTURE

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PhD

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Abstract. In the second half of the XX century, a significant event took place in the Karakalpak national song and dance art, the folk ensemble "Aykulash" was founded. The ensemble laid the foundation of the choreographic art of Karakalpakstan with its creative activity. His repertoire has become a model of folk art. For 65 years of its creative activity, the ensemble has created a singing and dance school in Karakalpakstan. The ensemble presented its unique repertoire to the peoples of the world.

Keywords: art, choreography, musical art, national culture, dance, Karakalpak dance, folk songs, male dance, folklore ensemble, spiritual heritage, cultural ties.

УСЛУГА ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛЕЙ СОВРЕМЕННОГО МУЗЫКАЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА В КАРАКАЛПАКСКОЙ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ

Аннотация. Во второй половине XX века в каракалпакском национальном песенно-танцевальном искусстве произошло знаменательное событие, был основан фольклорный ансамбль «Айкулаш». Своей творческой деятельностью ансамбль заложил основы хореографического искусства Каракалпакстана. Его репертуар стал образцом народного творчества. За 65 лет своей творческой деятельности ансамбль создал в Каракалпакстане школу песни и танца. Ансамбль представил свой уникальный репертуар народам мира.

Ключевые слова: искусство, хореография, музыкальное искусство, национальная культура, танец, каракалпакский танец, народные песни, мужской танец, фольклорный ансамбль, духовное наследие, культурные связи.

INTRODUCTION

XX century the national training on musical art, prepared by the organizers and musicians, took place. Karakalpak people from the 60s of the 20th century had the opportunity to listen to music in the direction of music along with the music of a pair of strings duthor and do – choir, symphony, opera and ballet.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the musical culture of Karakalpakstan, the role of Bakhshi, sozanda and composer Japaq Shamurodov is great in the formation and development of composers ' creativity. As a result of his tireless research, note-writing programs were formed in Karakalpak music, and early musical works began to be created in the kamer-vocal direction. He wrote about 200 songs, chants, choral, and music of P'essas. J. Shamuradov became the first chairman of the Union of composers of Karakalpakstan. J. After shamurodov a. Khalimov, X. Tordogolav, N. Mukhammeddinov, G. Demesinov, S. Paloanov, A. Sultanov, G. Amaniyazov, Q. Professional composers such as Zaretidinov brought new opportunities to The Musical Art of Karakalpakstan. The Karakalpak people still love and listen to the great talents of Khudoyberdi Turdikulov, Abdreyim Sultanov, Najimetdin Mukhameddinov. For the wonderful music that Abdreyim Sultanov wrote to the poems of Ajiniyaz, the Berdaq State Prize was awarded. Many of the

music of the composer Khudoyberdi Turdigulov was staged, and the weekly scene took place from the front lines of the programs.

The famous composer in the development of musical art of Karakalpakstan is people's artist of Uzbekistan A.Khalimov's services are incomparable. He studied in depth the centuries-old musical culture and art of the Karakalpak people and put many Karakalpak folk poems into notes. As a composer, he composed music for more than 15 performances. A.Khalimov composed more than 250 melodies for musical drama, comedy, vocal, Symphonic Choir and comedic works. He published the famous masterpieces of his life devoted to art in 1959, a work called "Qoraqalpoq xalq nomalari" in Tashkent.

Composer X. Turdikulov is known for his music that attracts young people through close to heart and lyrical feelings. For example, the poet I. To the word Yusupov "Menin jigiti uaktim senin qiz uaktin", T. To the word Yesemuratov "Juldizlar", T.To the word Matmuratov "kizlardin", "senin har kelgenin bahor kelgandey", R.To the word Duysemuratova "Keulimdi kiymayman", K.To the word Rakhmanov together with the works "my Uatanim seni jirlyayman" S."Taluas" By Khozhaniyazov, T."Jalinlar" Of The Seytjaniv, F.Nazarov and J.Aymurzaev wrote works on the plays "Sheberkhannin shirmagi".

Among the Karakalpak composers, the creator Abdreyim Sultanov is distinguished by his style of creativity, richness of his works in fantasy and nationality. The talented composer is known as the author of a large number of Public songs, choral works, symphonies of music, which he wrote down to dramatic works. A number of musical works written by Sultanov in the word Ajiniyaz took place in the Golden fund of the Karakalpakstan radio company.

A significant contribution to the last quarter-century revival of the musical art of Karakalpakstan was made by the outstanding composer, honored art figure of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Najimatdin Mukhammeddinov. More than a hundred of his music took a worthy place in the treasury of Karakalpak art. The ballet "Ayjamal" with Mukhammetddinov's opera "Ajiniyaz" testifies to the fact that the composer is the owner of an inimitable talent. The songs he created were performed by the most talented singers.

Composer Kenesbay Abdullaev was one of the first in the Republic of Karakalpakstan to compose a bayan-accordion Orchestra from students of a music school. Together with being the chief conductor of the ensemble of folk instruments under the Republican broadcasting company, he created music for more than 100 children, national dance teams, performances.

Ganiy Amaniayazov's role in enriching the art of Karakalpak music with various genres was high, he created lyric works entitled "On segiz bahar", "Izledim seni", "qong'irattin qizlari bor", "qora ko'z", "Kerdin-be", "Qiyalarim", "Bakhitli balalar" choral column and more than 350 musical works.

A significant contribution to the development of Karakalpak musical culture was made by M. Zhiyemuratov occupies a special place in the development of our national music. His "Aydin" music has become the classical music of the karakalpaks, which he performs with longing. M. Zhiyemuratov wrote the symphony poem of the same name in 1973, dedicated to Ernazar Olako, and the ballet "Makaria Sulu" in 1974. Playwright P.Tlegenov wrote music for the musical drama "Duotarli soldat". He presented 98 music to the people by publishing 110 of the Bakhshis' music in book form.

"Uzbekistanga xizmat ko'rsatgan artist" people's artist of "Karakalpakstan xalq artisti" S.Paluanov, as a composer, conductor, choreographer, wrote works for Song, Choir, Symphony and theater. He has recreated many Karakalpak folk music and presented it to the public.

In the 70-80s of the last century, the composer Ziyuatdin Lipesov, who had an audience with his lyrical songs, created in his work more than 100 melodies on the themes of Homeland, labor, courage. Z.Lipesov introduced many talents to the people through the competitions "Village mornings", "Boyterak", which were held on television in the 1970s and 1980s.

In 1980, composers of the younger generation took a step towards the art of music of Karakalpakstan with their creativity. One of these is the composer Q.Zaretdinov actively participated in the staging of the first Karakalpak National Opera "Ajiniyaz" as a conductor of days of culture in Tatarstan, Kazakhstan and Tashkent .

In the 1980s, one of the young composers Sharafatdin Pakhratdinov was known for the music "Nurli makonim", "Majnuntol", "Bagu and boston", "Urush veteranlariga", "Bir gul ko'rindi ketdi".

Composer Sharapatdin Pakhratdinov headed the Aydin ensemble, which was formed from Karakalpak students studying in Tashkent during their years at the Tashkent Conservatory.

In the second half of the 20th century, Karakalpakstan composers, composers, musicians and choral conductors made a significant contribution to the enrichment of Karakalpak musical art with various genres and the recognition of new musical works to the peoples of the world.

In the 50-80 years of the XX century, Karakalpakstan occupies a special place in the activities of solo performers in the development of singing art. Of these, Ayimkhan Shamuratova received the title of "people's artist of the USSR" in 1968. Along with playing the main roles in the Karakalpak State Theater, he also sang songs of fraternal peoples.

In the 50-60 years of the XX century, the upbringing of solo singers was known by Jolimbetova (1917-1963), Gulkhan Sherazieva (1920-1978), Arzigul Atamuratova (1923-2017), stop Rachmanova (1934), Fatima Bekpolatova, Tileuhan Akhmedova, Suliukhan Matyakubova and Suliukan Mambetova. They took a deep place in the heart of the people through their skillfully performed songs in their repertoire. People's artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan Gulkhan Sherozieva, along with playing the main role in musical performances, inherited Karakalpak folk songs in his repertoire.

People's artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan Arzigul Atamuratova has devoted more than 40 years of her life to the development of the art of Karakalpakstan. Arzigul Atamurotova "Dembermes", "Eshbay". He performed the songs "Jeti asirim", "Bes perde", "Bahar suygen yar", "Bugun baxt bag'indamiz", "Tang samallari", "nekis gulleri", "bagman qiz", "Yar-yar".

In the 60-80s of the XX century, Karakalpak girls, known for their tender voice, made folk songs known to the world. In the days of literature and culture of Karakalpakstan, which took place in Moscow in 1959, Gulparshin Sirimbetova performed the song "Deryasan". The songs "Dem bermes", "Nalish", "Do'stima", "yo'llarim" by the owner of istedad Tamara Dorshumova remained in the people's memory as indelible Navos.

In the 60s and 70s of the XX century, an excellent talent Dao'itbay Kayipov for seven years of his work received a place in the heart of the Karakalpak people with his unique songs, sonorous voice.

In the 80s of the XX century, processed variants of Karakalpak national songs appeared in the variety direction. The services of Dautboy Kayipov, Zamira Khozhanazarova, who raised

the Karakalpak variety by one step, were great in it. Z. Khajanazarova "Anajanim", "talqin", " who was Janim kimdi jaqsi ko'resen? the word G.Music of Shamuratova D.Janabaeva. "qaylarda eding muxabbat?Performing arias from the musical drama" shag'alalar"," Bahar Shamali"," Kelmeding"," Mag'an kelip ket"," Tuyilgan jer"," Ayraliq"," Berdaq " enriched Karakalpak national singing art.

These two talents became known to the country for their short life with the art of Karakalpak execution and were regarded as "so'nmas yulduzlar", revered among the people. The repertoire of Bayram Matjanov (1940-2020), known for his 37 years of work, which contributed to the development of Karakalpak singing art, with a pleasant voice, lively feelings and a stage culture that attracts listeners, is popularly known as a rich innovator performer. B. Matzhanov paid special attention to the synchronicity of music with the meaning of words, paying special attention to the issue of choosing a repertoire. B.Matzhanov introduced the art of Karakalpak singing to fraternal peoples and received the title of people's artist of Uzbekistan, Bashkirdistan, Karakalpakstan and state awards.

RESULTS

People's artist of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Karakalpakstan Kamiljon Otaniyozov said among his students that Atajon Khudayshukurov "on the other side of the Amudarya there is a talented young man who is distinguished from his peers by the voice given by Allah. It is said by his father Khudayshukurov. Both tomorrow's Nightingale and pride of the bust of art will be that young man." Father Khudayshukurov has been working as a solo singer in the Karakalpak State Philharmonic since 1963. Along with classical songs, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Karakalpak, Kazakh and Kyrgyz folk songs were included in his work. O.Khudayshukurov, along with the singer, musician, is also known as the composer of more than 300 songs, such as " Mujgonlarning ", "olamda bir ", "birinchi muxabbatim". To Him " O.Khudayshukurov was attractive, timbre, with a smooth and sonorous voice in all curtains. It was not for nothing that such qualities in his songs as passion, enthusiasm and enthusiasm, and depth in content took a deep place in the hearts of the audience."

Bazarboy Nodirov, Gulparshin Sirimbetova, Bibiraba Utepbergenova, Tursingul Kayipnazarova, Tursinbay Palimbetov, Utebay Temirkhanov, Tamara Doshumova, Marjangul Tileomuratova, Sveta Shinikulova, Makhset Matekov, Hanzada Paloanova, Perikhan Alibekova, who created a unique school in the national singing art of Karakalpakstan in the 70-80s of the XX century left an indelible mark on national singing art with.

Ida Rafikova, Ilyich Khodjametov, Maxset Khozhaniyazov, Davlet Atajanov, Kenesboy Serzhanov, Gulhatiysha Ayimbetova, Bazargul Karimova, Dalibay Mambetmuratov, Mirzagul Sapaeva, Rosa Kutekeeva brought the Karakalpak national singing art to a new level. The fact that the talented singer Maxset Khozhaniyazov was a prize winner at the International Festival in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, a laureate of the Central Asian Festival of vocalists took an important place in the world recognition of the art of Karakalpak singing.

Ilich Khodjametov also played a great role in the development of the variety route in Karakalpakstan. I.Khodjametov organized the revyu variety ensemble "qirq qiz" under the Karakalpak State Philharmonic named after Berdak. From the singers of the ensemble a.Bayarkina, L.Koshan (Russia), I.Vakhlakov (Baku) I.Khadjametav, Q.Allayarov, M.Tileomuratova, O.Temirkhanov, D.Mambetmuratov, M.Artikova, Z.Kamalova, G.Monteeva, M.Tajigalieva, Zamira and Inkar Khojanazarova, V.Chaban from dancers S.Dospanova, Zarema

and Lola Rafikova, I.Loseva, I.Shvalova, I.Number, I.Li, A.Kalikovas made a great contribution to the development of the variety genre in the art of Karakalpakstan. The first time the ensemble performed works from the repertoire of foreign performers, Uzbek, Karakalpak folk songs and taronas. In particular, the songs "Muxabbatinan", "Tashkent oqshomi", "Qora tollar", "Tuug'an jerge", "Shag'ala", "To'lqin" are preserved in the people's memory to this day. In 1981, the ensemble "Forty Girls" was called variety-choreographic Revue, and the artistic director D.M.Tarleev and chief ballet player D. Yusupov was engaged in work.

1981-1982 with the ensemble concert program, they toured South Sakhalin, the Far East, Kamchatka, the Caucasus, Crimea, Moldavia, the Republic of Buryatia, in 1983 in the cities of Magadan, Chita, Ulan-Ude, in 1986 in the republics of Moykop, Ukraine, Vilnius, Riga, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan. Especially Muyassar Razzakova, Rosa Qutekeeva, Eliza Aitniyazova contributed to the recognition of Karakalpak opera, folk songs all over the world.

DISCUSSION

A Republican competition of Bakhshi performers was organized in Tashkent, dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Japaq Bakhshi Shamuratov, at which the Karakalpakstan T.Gurbanov, M.Pirnazarov, young singer a.Aytiniyazov won.

In 1992, 11 competitions and Memorial evenings were held dedicated to the anniversaries of art artists. In Particular, Japaq Bakshi Shamuratov, Ayimkhan Shamuratova, A.Khajalepesov, E.Gaspalatav, C.Bekmuratov, D.Qayipov, Z.Festivals of young talented people were organized in memory of khozhanazarova. The festivals were attended by guests from Tashovuz, Khorezm and Bukhara region of Turkmenistan.

The days of culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan were held in Tashkent on January 25-29, 1993. During these days of culture, literary and art artists of Karakalpakstan presented concert programs at the State Theater and stage of Tashkent City. A group of Karakalpak artists are awarded honorary titles of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of These, T.Kayipbergenov "O'zbekistan xalq yozuvchisi", G.Aymbetova, M.Sapayeva, R.Saparova and B.Kayipovs title "O'zbekiston xalq artisti", chief correspondent of the magazine "Aral qizlari" G.Esemuratova is awarded the title of "honored cultural figure of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2007 Actress of Karakalpak state musical theater Sarbinaz Annakulova became laureate of the Nihal prize. As a theater actress, she starred in the play "Alpomish" in Gulbarshin, S.Aysanem in the play by hojaniyazov "Suymaganga suykalma", K.Rakhmanov in the play "Yor diydari" created the images of the main character in Maqqal and many other performances.

In 2008, Variety singer late Rashid Khojasov, the winner of the "Nihol" award, was highly appreciated for his service as a real talent and was awarded the honorable title "Qoraqalpog'istonda xizmat ko'rsatgan artist".

In recent years, Aygul Nadirova has been noticed for her skills in performing folk songs and national songs of the variety direction. In his performance, folk songs were sung, modernizing the songs "Nalish" and "Yuring qizlar", N.Muhammedinov, "Yor-yor aytayin", J.Shamuratov's songs "Estelik ettim oramal" performed with high skill in the national style.

Independence has taken an important place in the recognition of our talented youth on the world stage. In particular, the "O'zbekiston va Qoraqalpog'istonda xizmat ko'rsatgan artist", Jenisbek Piyazov, with his special talent for creativity in the opera direction, was able to receive the "Nihol" award in 2007. Jenisbek Piyazov took part in competitions held in such countries as

France, Spain, Portugal, Russia, Malaysia, Kazakhstan. In 2010, in accordance with the presidential decree, he was awarded the Medal of Fame. J.Piyazov's tireless work in introducing national art to the world was highly appreciated, in 2014 he was awarded the title of "O'zbekistonda xizmat ko'rsatgan artist", in 2021—"O'zbekiston Respublikasi artisti".

CONCLUSIONS

During the independence period, the folklore and ethnographic ensemble "AMU wave" occupies an important place in the supply of musical treasures of the Karakalpak people to generations. People's artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan Gylkhatiysha Ayimbetova, honored artists of the Republic of Karakalpakstan Bakhtiyar Yesemuratov, Salamat Kalibekov, Sultan Kasekyev showed their abilities in performing folk and modern songs from the members of the ensemble.

The establishment of the State prize named after Zulfiya by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 10, 1999 took a huge place in the material and spiritual support of the creative and active people of gifted youth. To date, more than 20 girls have won the Zulfiya State Prize in the Republic of Karakalpakstan since 2000.

The "germination" award opened a wide path to the identification of young talent and their further improvement from creative abilities. The first winner of the award from the Republic of Karakalpakstan was the talented singer Makset Utemuratov. In subsequent years, Dilfuza Bekimbetova, Gulnar Aljanova, Eleonora Qutlibulatova, Gulnaz Utepova, Sarbinaz Annakulova, Jenisbek Piyazov, Rashid Khojasov, Gulbar Abipova, Zhat Bekchanov, Lola Muhammadinova, G.Akhimbetova, Janibek Piyazov, Adilbek Bakhtibayev, Naorizbek Mahammadiyarov became winners of the "Nihol" prize.

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